

Title: Artificial Intelligence Strategy: Delivering Deep Learning

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Abstract:

Within the worlds of artificial intelligence and machine learning, deep learning is where a continual stream of the most exciting advancements are being made - it is amazing AI that works today, and it is the driving force behind the current AI / ML revolution.

Deep learning will impact nearly every industry on the planet, and there will be countless opportunities to take advantage of this technology. Google CEO Sundar Pichai asserts that while the last decade was about 'mobile-first', the next decade will be about 'AI-first'. Deep learning is where many of the most significant innovations in AI are occurring - self-driving cars, self-organizing drone swarms, computer vision, conversational interfaces, advanced industrial robots, speech recognition, emotion recognition, etc.,

Even so, reaping the benefits of deep learning is hard to achieve. Success requires a well-considered AI strategy that accommodates business drivers, data acquisition and preparation, model architecture, algorithm selection, robust cloud infrastructure, service integration, delivery mechanisms, etc.,

Over the next decade, deep learning models will become common microservices within enterprises architectures. Software engineers will be expected to design, develop, and deploy deep learning microservices into production.

In this presentation, we will address strategy for delivering deep learning into production, and explore how deep learning is integrated into a modern enterprise architecture. Along the way, we will analyze various AI implementation strategies, the prerequisite data strategies that specific AI strategy depend upon, and the trade-offs that each approach implies.

As a global leader in applying artificial intelligence to advanced robotics and the 'Internet of Things' (IoT), Honeywell will provide us with practical examples of AI strategy and implementation choices that illustrate world-class AI-driven product development.

KEYWORDS:

Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Neural Networks, Data Science

BIOGRAPHY:

Chris Benson is Chief Scientist, Artificial Intelligence & Machine Learning for one of the four global strategic business groups at Honeywell – Safety & Productivity Solutions - where he is responsible for all AI initiatives across all product lines.

He is an AI strategist, solution architect, and public speaker / evangelist, who specializes in deep learning - the machine learning discipline that is driving the artificial intelligence revolution.

Chris frequently speaks about various AI topics at conferences, and is the Founder & Organizer of the Atlanta Deep Learning Meetup, one of the largest AI communities in the world.